

Synthesis of some Potential Antibacterial Sulphonamoylazopyrimidines

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A pyrimidine ring is well known for its biological significance¹. Many derivatives of pyrimidine has been used as therapeutic agents². The antibacterial activity of sulphadiazine against various diseases is a well established fact³. Hence, it was felt useful to bring pyrimidine nucleus and sulphonamoyl grouping within a molecular framework to enhance biological activity of the new compound.

Treatment of acetylacetone with different diazonium salts in presence of sodium acetate gave 1,3-dimethyl-2-[4'-(substituted)sulphonamoyl]hydrazonopropane-1,3-

Varian spectrophotometer (270 MHz) using TMS as the internal standard. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel-G plates. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

1,3-Dimethyl-2-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazonopropane-1,3-dione (1a) : The starting sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of conc. HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-salt bath. Cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) was added to it in portions. Diazonium salt so formed was filtered into already cooled (0°) solution mixture of sodium acetate (8 g) and acetylacetone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), and the solution was stirred vigorously. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 195°; λ_{\max} 364 nm; ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH), 1 720, 1 670 (CO involved in H-bonding), 1 110 cm^{-1} (SO_2); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.30 (6H, s, 2 × COCH_3), 14.60 (1H, s, NH H-bonded), 7.50–8.20 (4H, m, substituted phenyl). Similarly other compounds (all yellow coloured crystals) of the series were prepared by coupling appropriate sulphonamide with acetylacetone : **1b** (60%), m.p. 215°; **c** (65%), 210°; **d** (70%), 201°; **e** (55%), 205°.

2-Amino-4,6-dimethyl-(4'-sulphonamoyl)azopyrimidine (2a) : An alcoholic solution of **1a** (0.001 mol) was added to a solution of guanidine nitrate (0.001 mol) in a methanolic 1.0 N NaOH solution and the mixture was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool overnight and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 47°; λ_{\max} 346.0 nm; λ_{\max} 3 320 (NH_2), 1 610 (N=N), 1 660 (C=N or C=C), 1 135 (SO_2) and 750 cm^{-1} (phenyl); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.50 (6H, s, 2 CH_3), 3.8 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.2–7.9 (4H, m, substituted phenyl). Similarly other compounds (all brown coloured crystals) were prepared : **2b** (65%), m.p. 50°; **c** (60%), 55°; **d** (62%), 58°; **e** (58%), 60°.

Scheme 1

diones (**1a-e**), which on condensation with guanidine nitrate in methanolic 1.0 N NaOH solution yielded 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-(substituted)-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidine (**2a-e**).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 833 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a

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